

Space Health Programming, Health Information Resources to Support Science Engagement – an SCR Initiative

Author/Creator: Debbie Montenegro, UNT Health Science Center

Program Details

Title: Space Health Programming, Health Information Resources to Support Science Engagement, an SCR Initiative

Dates: 2017 - 2020

Locations: Houston, TX, Cape Canaveral, Florida, Dallas, TX, and multiple locations in Fort Worth, TX.

Venues: Multiple conferences, including national conferences at Space Center Houston and Kennedy Space Center. Public libraries across the Dallas/Fort Worth area.

Audience: Science Educators, information science specialists/librarians, conference attendees, the public, and the local community.

Program Overview

Space Health Programming, Health Information Resources to Support Science Engagement

- Project Development - Program Design, Curriculum, Course, Manual, educational Aid Techniques
- Network Building and Site Visits
- Cross-disciplinary collaboration
- Public Programming and Community Outreach
- State, Regional, and National Conference Presentations

Initiative

Space Health Programming, Health Information Resources to Support Science Engagement was developed by the Consumer Health Coordinator to provide NNLM, NLM, NIH, and NASA resources to train science educators, information specialists, and outreach to the public. This was a regional engagement plan that contributed to the overall NNLM mission and evolved into collaborations at the national level. Specific programs came about due to network building, site visits, and cross-disciplinary collaborations. Archived URL: [link](#)

An SCR Regional Initiative for engagement. Initiatives were led by South Central Region coordinators to help utilize their unique expertise to contribute to the mission of NNLM and to the NLM Objectives.

The mission of the NNLM is to advance the progress of medicine and improve the public health by providing all U.S. health professionals with equal access to biomedical information and improving the public's access to information to enable them to make informed decisions about their health.

NLM Objective 2.1: Know NLM users and engage with persistence

NLM Objective 3.4: Engage the next generation and promote data literacy

Key Topics Covered

- Astronaut Health: Health Information Resources to Support Science Education
- NASA Solar System Ambassadors program
- Mars Anomalies: STEM and literacy collaborations with health connections
- Astronaut Academy: Health and Exercise - community engagement collaboration
- 50th anniversary of the Apollo moon landing - SSA collaboration

Overview of Events

National Conferences - Collaborations

Parker, L., Montenegro, D., et al. (2019, July). *Mars Anomalies: Exploring Literacy and STEM Collaborations with Health Connections*. [National conference presentation & educational aid techniques]. Space Port Area Conference for Educators (SPACE), **Kennedy Space Center**, Cape Canaveral, Florida. Conference archived at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20191114200228/https://www.kennedyconference.org/program>

Parker, L., Montenegro, D., et al. (2019, February). *Mars Anomalies: Exploring Literacy and STEM Collaborations with Health Connections*. [National conference presentation & educational aid techniques]. Space Exploration Educators Conference (SEEC), invited as the Expert for the Expert/Educator series, **Space Center Houston**, Houston, TX. Montenegro, D., was invited as the Expert for the Expert/Educator series at the SEEC conference. Conference session archived at: <https://sites.grenadine.co/sites/spacecenter/en/seec2019/schedule/287/ExpertEducator%3AMarsAnomalies%3AExploringLiteracyandSTEMCollaborations?platform=>

National Course Material and Webinars

Montenegro D. (2019). *Astronaut Health: Health Information Resources to Support Science Education*. [National class page and course materials]. NNLM. Retrieved from: https://web.archive.org/web/20190822053126/https://nnlm.gov/classes/astronaut_health
Footnote: Utilizing the challenges faced in space health to direct participants to resources.

Montenegro D. (2019, April 23). *Astronaut Health: Science Information Resources*. [National webinar]. NNLM. Retrieved from:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20210404012944/https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=itM7gsNqQ94>

Montenegro D. (2019, December 5). *Astronaut Health: Health Information Resources to Support Science Education*. [National webinar]. NNLM. Retrieved from: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1F_Wl5cs9bl

Footnote: NNLM National webinars were eligible for CE credit. Included a new section introducing the NASA Solar System Ambassadors program, as the creator became a NASA Solar System Ambassador in January of 2019.

National Manual - Collaboration

Boyd, L., Montenegro, D., et al. (2019). *A Universe of Stories, 2019 Summer Health Programming Manual* [activity manual]. NNLM. Archived at: https://web.archive.org/web/20201017194355/https://nnlm.gov/sites/default/files/shared/files/Public_Libraries/SummerReading2019/NNLM_Summer_Reading_Manual_2019.pdf

Footnote: Montenegro, D. served as the primary contributing author of educational content in the NNLM Summer of Space Health Program Manual, an outreach curriculum program manual companion to the CSLP Summer of Space manual. Intersection of space exploration and human health, including hands-on activities.

Regional Conference

Montenegro, D. (2018, July 20). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math) Librarians South Conference (regional conference covering southern states); Houston, TX. NNLM. This was the conference session opener, in-person. Retrieved from: <https://uh-ir.tdl.org/items/7b41483a-a47e-4d58-89da-c74d639cbdff>

State Conferences

Parker, L., Montenegro, D., et al. (2018, November 1). *Mars Anomalies: Exploring Literacy and STEM Collaborations with Health Connections*. [Conference presentation]. Science Teachers Association of Texas CAST Conference for the Advancement of Science Teaching. Fort Worth, Texas. Conference URL: <https://s6.goeshow.com/sam/cast/2018/sessions.cfm>

Montenegro D. (2018, April 5). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. TxLA. Dallas, Texas. NNLM. This session was kindly attended by Astronaut Clayton Anderson. Conference program: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/160djHFwuiO6hojiVbor0En25n1IRQIF5/view>

Montenegro D. (2018, April 23). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. AIIM, Arkansas Association of Instructional Media. Little

Rock, Arkansas. NNLM. Conference URL:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20191022010912/https://www.aaimk12.org/2018-conference-links--resources.html>

Montenegro D. (2018, April 24). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. AIIM, Arkansas Association of Instructional Media. Little Rock, Arkansas. NNLM. Conference URL:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20191022010912/https://www.aaimk12.org/2018-conference-links--resources.html>

Montenegro D. (2018, March). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. LLA, Alexandria, Louisiana. NNLM. Conference URL:
https://web.archive.org/web/20190922124821/https://llaonline.org/LLA/Events/Past_Events/2018_Annual_Conference/General_Conference_Information/LLA/Events/2018Conference/2018_Conference_Landing.aspx?hkey=f3397005-7fd8-4243-a23b-b9945a3d14f8

Montenegro D. (2017, November). *Astronaut Health: Science Education Resources*. [Conference presentation]. NMLA, Albuquerque, New Mexico. NNLM. Conference URL:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20181002120602/http://nmla.org/annual-conference/>

Invited Speaker Events

Montenegro, D. (2019, March 15). *Launching Your Year of Space! With NNLM and the Solar System Ambassadors*. [Invited conference speaker presentation]. Government Documents Round Table (GODORT) Breakfast & Business Meeting of LLA, Baton Rouge, Louisiana. Conference archived at: [link](#)

Montenegro, D. (Guest Expert). (2019, April 30). WERO (Host). Invited guest expert speaker: Debbie Montenegro (Season 1, Episode 9). [Audio podcast episode]. Wero: A Community Podcast. Apple Podcasts. URL:
<https://podcasts.apple.com/us/podcast/wero/id1455268399>

Podcast summary: NASA Solar System Ambassador - Debbie Montenegro. We talk about science (in a way the rest of us can understand!), space travel ... and how NASA research relates to all of us.

Local Public Programming and Outreach

Sheldon, L., Montenegro, D., Parker, L., & collaborators. (2019, Summer). *Astronaut Academy: Health & Exercise* – multi-session series. [Unpublished curriculum and educational outreach program]. Fort Worth Public Library system, UNT Health Science Center, & community partners. URL: [link](#)

Footnote: Montenegro, D participated in 10 individual sessions at 10 different locations. Outreach program for the public across several branches and low-income apartment communities.

Murry, L., Montenegro, D., & collaborators. (2019, July 20). *Apollo 11: 50th Anniversary Lunar Landing Exhibit*. [Exhibit and educational program]. J. Erik Jonsson Central Library, Dallas Public Library System. URL to event: [link](#)
Acknowledgment: NASA Solar System Ambassadors collaboration

Janney, D., et. al. (2018, November 15). *NASA Mosquito Citizen Science Project* [Webinar]. SCR CONNECTIONS, NNLM South Central Region. Archived at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20210407032321/https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=11dsxwSuing>

Acknowledgment: Montenegro, D., recruited the guest speaker and provided technical support for the webinar session.

Site Visits, Networking & Communications

Site Visits

- NASA Department of Education, Houston, TX
- The Space Archive at the University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston (UTMB), Galveston, TX
- Local middle school with a NASA Solar System Ambassador science teacher, TX

Regional public blog posts

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, September 12). *Summer Report – Part 3: The Year of Space* [Blog post]. NNLM SCR Blogadillo. Archived at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20190915122803/https://news.nnlm.gov/scr/public-libraries-summer-report-part-3-the-year-of-space-in-libraries-schools-and-the-community/>

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, August 27). *Summer Report – Part 2: NNLM Summer Reading Collaborations* [Blog post]. NNLM SCR Blogadillo. Archived at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20201101135415/https://news.nnlm.gov/scr/public-libraries-summer-report-part-2-nnlm-summer-reading-collaborations/>

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, August 20). *Summer Report – Part 1: The Oklahoma Symposium*. [Blog post]. NNLM SCR Blogadillo. Archived at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20201127082717/https://news.nnlm.gov/scr/public-libraries-summer-report-part-1-the-oklahoma-symposium/>

Social Media posts

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, September 12). Post linking to Summer Report: Part 3: The Year of Space blog post. [Facebook post]. NNLM Region 3 (formerly NNLM South Central Region).

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, August 27). Post linking to Summer Report: Part 2 blog. [Facebook post]. NNLM Region 3 (formerly NNLM South Central Region).

Montenegro, D, and Leaf, B. (2019, August 20). Post linking to Summer Report: Part 1 blog. [Facebook post]. NNLM Region 3 (formerly NNLM South Central Region).

Impact and Outcomes

NNLM Key Accomplishment

The 2019 Summer Health Programming Manual was one of the top three key accomplishments at the national level for all NNLM for that year.

Speaker Invitations & National Collaborative Presentations

Presenting at several state conferences around the region, networking, and sharing via the office blog and social media outlets led to invitations to speak at the GODORT meeting of a conference and another invitation to be the guest speaker for a podcast. Networking also paved the way for invitations to collaborate in other outreach programs. Targeted site visits and networking at conferences fostered collaborations that led to presentations at national conferences and outreach programs. Cross-disciplinary collaborations were forged with K-12 educators, health science librarians, public libraries, a community persona and podcaster, and other NASA Solar System Ambassadors. This regional initiative evolved into national-level programming, reaching far more participants directly, thanks to networking and collaboration.

Acknowledgments

This resource was supported by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH), under Cooperative Agreement number UG4LM012345 with the University of North Texas Health Science Center in Fort Worth, TX. The content is solely the responsibility of the author and does not necessarily represent the official views of the National Institutes of Health.

Contact Information

Name: Debbie Montenegro

Email: Debbie.Montenegro@unthsc.edu

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0519-7418>

Institution: UNT Health Science Center

Archive Note

This document provides a citable and accessible record of the above presentation for research documentation purposes. It is archived to demonstrate professional qualifications and contributions to the field.